

Investigating Spelling Errors in High-Functioning Dyslexic and Non-Dyslexic Learners
of English as a Foreign Language
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In this presentation, we compare the proportion and the nature of spelling errors made by learners of English as a foreign language (L2) with dyslexia to those made by a control group. Our approach relies on data representing both the written product and the writing process.

Dyslexia is commonly associated with spelling difficulties, which persist into adulthood (Callens et al., 2012), even among high-functioning dyslexics (Gallagher et al., 1996), i.e. adults who were diagnosed with dyslexia in childhood but have compensated sufficiently to undertake higher education. Most studies focusing on the impact of dyslexia in writing concern children and L1, and the few studies focusing on adults show contradictory findings (Tops et al., 2014). It therefore seems relevant to investigate spelling errors and their nature in high-functioning dyslexics writing in L2 as dyslexia-related difficulties may be more pronounced in an L2 (Helland & Kaasa, 2005).

In line with previous research on dyslexia (Tops et al., 2014), we distinguished three categories of spelling errors: phonological spelling errors, occurring when a word is inaccurately spelled based on its pronunciation, grammatical spelling errors, occurring when spelling violates a language-specific spelling rule, and orthographical spelling errors, occurring when an incorrect grapheme is used to represent a phoneme. Our objective is to investigate which type(s) of spelling errors is/are most prevalent and to what extent in several high-functioning dyslexic learners and non-dyslexic learners based on short narrative texts written in L1 and L2.

The data collected are part of PROCEED (Gilquin, 2022), a learner corpus of English that includes written texts, but also keylogging (Inputlog; Leijten & Van Waes, 2013) and screencasting data (OBS Studio; Jim & OBS Studio Contributors, 2021), making the writing process visible. Stimulated recall sessions are also performed to get a better understanding of learners' cognitive activities during the writing task.

References

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